

Predicting wear in reinforced,

The choice of lubricants and reinforcements greatly affects wear life in both plastic-metal and plastic-plastic interfaces.

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Thermoplastics have become a prime design material for gears, cams, bearings, slides, ratchets and similar moving mechanical components. Their wear properties have expanded steadily with the introduction of new engineering plastics, and, particularly with the growth of compounding technology using fillers, reinforcements and internal lubricants.

Through compounding, frictional properties can be reduced and improvements can be attained in load-carrying capacity and wear life. Heat resistance, fatigue endurance, creep resistance, dimensional stability and part-to-part reproducibility are improved also.

The main criteria for evaluating a plastic compound for wear-type applications are: frictional properties, wear rate and limiting pressure-velocity (LPV). While the base resin is obviously a prime factor in performance, optimum wear properties depend heavily on additive technology.

Over the past decade LNP Corp. has formulated and tested hundreds of thermoplastic compounds specifically for sliding and rolling-type service. Data has been accumulated on a wide assortment of resins, comparing wear properties for various combinations of fillers, reinforcements and internal lubricants. Since the data is far too voluminous to present in a single article (LNP will publish a comprehensive wear-properties handbook early next year), this article will review, in general terms, the effects of the most common additives on wear in reinforced plastics.

The discussion will cover wear in both plastic-metal and plastic-plastic combinations. Performance will be discussed in terms of the three principal "wear parameters": coeffi-

cient of friction, wear factor and LPV.

All quantitative coefficient of friction and wear-factor data presented in the article were obtained from a thrust-washer test apparatus. In this setup, a "washer" of the test material, mounted in a powered spindle, is rotated at a known speed and contact force against a washer of the mating material (a carbon-steel "standard" or another plastic) mounted in the anti-friction idler spindle (see drawing).

The frictional properties of thermoplastic composites differ in a unique way from metals. In contrast to metals, even highly-reinforced resins have low modulus values and therefore do not follow the classic laws of friction.

Metal-thermoplastic friction is characterized by adhesion and deformation. As a result, the frictional forces are not proportional to load (friction decreases as load increases), but they are proportional to speed.

Wear and wear factor

Several mechanisms are involved in material wear at a wear interface. The primary mechanism is adhesive wear, in which particles of polymer are plucked from one surface as a result of adhesion to the other. The presence of fine powder is a good indication that the rubbing surfaces are wearing properly. However, if melted polymer or large gouges or grooves are present at the interface, the materials probably are abrading rather than wearing. Possibly the pressure-velocity limit of the material is being exceeded also.

Wear rate is generally defined as the volume of material lost per unit of time. Since the wear rate depends on the contact force and surface speed encountered in a given time, a more convenient basis to compare materials is the wear factor, K.

The wear factor is a number derived by dividing the volumetric wear observed during the test by the algebraic product of the force, surface speed and elapsed time. That is:

$$K = \frac{W}{FVT}, \text{ where}$$

W = material lost (cu in.)

F = applied force (lb)

V = surface speed (in./min.)

T = elapsed time (hr.)

Once a K factor is established, it can

be used to calculate the wear rates of bearings, gears, etc., in an application. However, because wear rate is affected by material type, finish, hardness, temperature and part design, large errors may result if end-use conditions differ from those used in the test. Still, as a relative measure of the performance of several compounds operating at the same conditions, the K factor is a highly reliable device.

Limiting PV

The load and velocity capability of a bearing material is expressed by the algebraic product of the unit load "P" (psi, based upon projected bearing area) and the linear velocity "V" (ft/min) of the test shaft. The symbol PV is used to express this pressure-velocity relationship.

The test from which LPV is calculated is a short-term test, independent of wear rate. When the in-use conditions exceed approximately one-half of the limiting PV, the wear rate begins to accelerate. For design purposes, therefore, the practical or "working" PV can be approximated by dividing the LPV values in half.

Internal lubricants

The primary lubricants used to improve the wear characteristics of reinforced thermoplastics are:

internally-lubricated thermoplastics

Table 1. Effect of various reinforcement, PTFE and silicone combinations on frictional wear and LPV properties of nylon 6/6 on carbon steel

Nylon 6/6 composition				Wear factor, K 10 ⁻¹⁰ in. ³ min/ ft/lb/hr	Coefficient of Friction		Limiting PV(LPV)		
PTFE Wt %	Silicone Wt %	Glass fiber Wt %	Carbon fiber Wt %		Static (40 psi)	Dynamic (40 psi, 50 fpm)	10 fpm	100 fpm	1000 fpm
—	—	—	—	200	0.20	0.28	3,000	2,500	2,500
5	—	—	—	60	0.13	0.20	—	—	—
20	—	—	—	12	0.10	0.18	14,000	17,500	8,000
—	2	—	—	40	0.09	0.09	3,000	6,000	9,000
18	2	—	—	6	0.06	0.08	14,000	30,000	12,000
—	—	10	—	80	0.21	0.28	—	—	—
—	—	20	—	80	0.23	0.30	—	—	—
—	—	30	—	75	0.25	0.31	12,500	10,000	7,500
—	—	40	—	70	0.26	0.33	—	—	—
—	—	50	—	60	0.28	0.35	—	—	—
15	—	30	—	16	0.19	0.26	17,500	20,000	17,500
13	2	30	—	9	0.12	0.14	17,000	20,000	19,000
—	—	—	20	40	0.16	0.20	—	—	—
—	—	—	30	20	0.16	0.20	21,000	27,000	8,000
—	—	—	40	14	0.13	0.18	—	—	—
15	—	—	30	10	0.11	0.15	29,000	42,000	19,000
13	2	—	30	6	0.10	0.11	29,000	43,000	20,000

Table 2. Effect of glass-fiber reinforcement, molybdenum disulfide and graphite-powder combinations of frictional and wear properties of nylon 6/6 on carbon steel

Reinforcement		MoS ₂ Wt. %	Graphite Wt. %	Wear factor, K 10 ⁻¹⁰ in. ³ min/ ft/lb/hr	Coefficient of friction	
Type	Wt. %				Static (40 psi)	Dynamic (40 psi, 50 fpm)
—	—	—	5	55	0.15	0.20
—	—	<5	—	150	0.28	0.30
Glass fiber	30	<5	—	75	0.24	0.31
Glass fiber	40	<5	—	70	0.26	0.33

PTFE: A low-molecular-weight modification of polytetrafluoroethylene.

Silicone: High viscosity, low-vapor-pressure polysiloxane liquid.

Other lubricants, such as graphite and molybdenum disulfide, are also used, but to a more limited extent.

Reinforcing materials, though added to improve mechanical properties, also affect wear properties. The principal reinforcements in wear-service compositions (discussed later in this article) are:

Carbon fiber: High modulus, highly graphitized fiber.

Glass fiber: 0.00045-in. dia, E-grade glass fiber.

Table 1 summarizes the effectiveness of PTFE and silicone in improving wear properties in reinforced thermoplastics, as typified by a nylon 6/6 series.

PTFE

Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) lubricants predispersed into a thermoplastic resin greatly improve its surface characteristics. This fluorocarbon has the lowest coefficient of friction (.05) of any known internal lubricant. Its static coefficient of friction is lower than its dynamic coefficient, which accounts for the slip-stick properties of a sliding PTFE-metal interface.

During an initial break-in period, PTFE particles are sheared from the thermoplastic matrix and form a high-lubricity film on the mating surface. This film serves to fill the low spots around asperities and cushion them from shock and subsequent fatigue failure.

For each family of bearing materials there is an optimum PTFE content. Adding PTFE beyond the optimum level will result in increased wear, though the coefficient of friction will continue to be reduced. The maximum loading depends on the ability to disperse the PTFE uniformly throughout the resin matrix. While the

optimum loading varies slightly for each resin system, it approaches 20 weight-percent for crystalline polymers and 15 weight-percent for amorphous and elastomeric resins.

Silicone

With the proper selection of the silicone and the use of special compounding techniques, a complete line of thermoplastics can be formulated with migratory-lubricant properties. The choice of the silicone is dictated by its ability to act as a boundary lubricant and by its degree of compatibility with the specific base resin. A properly selected silicone is sufficiently compatible with the base resin to form a partial alloy, yet incompatible enough to permit it to migrate to the surface of the compound. This migration continuously generates a polymer film that serves as a boundary or mixed-film lubricant.

Wear, friction, and PV properties can be improved further by using both a migratory-type lubricant (silicone) and PTFE. These materials combine at the wear surface to form a high-temperature grease. The PTFE acts both as a thickener and an extreme-pressure additive; while the silicone ensures continuous lubricity at startup and at high speeds, two conditions that can cause failure when PTFE is used alone.

Silicone produces the greatest improvement in the LPV at high velocities. This is to be expected because wear is a much bigger factor in high-speed failure than in low-speed failure. In PTFE/silicone-lubricated acetal running at 1000 fpm for example, the LPV is more than double that of the same acetal lubricated with PTFE only. Predictably, silicone is much less effective in bearings operating at low speeds and high pressures.

While PTFE and/or silicone are the most effective and versatile of the internal lubricants, other lubricants, mainly graphite powder and molybdenum disulfide, are useful in specific applications. Their properties are compared in Table 2.

Graphite powders

Graphite powders are the familiar low-friction, temperature-resistant solids widely used to provide boundary-lubrication protection for moving metal parts. Graphites are available in many varieties; their ability to lubricate depends on their structure, purity and particle size.

With the proper type and amount of

graphite, compounds can be produced with coefficients of friction and wear factors that fall between those of the unmodified base resin and the PTFE/silicone lubricated grades.

Graphite-lubricated thermoplastics are used mostly in aqueous environments. High graphite loadings (up to 30%) can also act as fillers to reduce mold shrinkage. When combined with mineral fillers in an amorphous polymer (SAN, Noryl, polysulfone, etc.), they provide compounds that are ideally suited for tight-tolerance wear components operating in an aqueous environment.

Molybdenum disulfide

Molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2) is another solid lubricant that can reduce wear rates and increase PV limits. Unlike PTFE and silicone, moly does not significantly reduce the coefficients of friction, and when used to lubricate a glass-reinforced resin, it gives the mating surface little or no protection against wear.

Molybdenum disulfide also acts as a nucleating agent. In nylon, its nucleating effect imparts a fine, even, crystalline structure to the molded part. This crystallinity results in bearing properties that are markedly superior to those obtained when molding unmodified nylon, whose outer skin is almost totally amorphous because of chilling by the mold surface. The nucleation effect of moly appears limited to nylons; little benefit is noted with other crystalline resins or with amorphous polymers.

In addition to improving surface characteristics, moly also improves the mechanical and thermal characteristics of nylons. Moly-lubricated nylons usually have faster molding cycles and slightly lower, but more uniform shrinkage characteristics. All of these property and processing improvements are attributed to the effect of nucleation on molecular configuration.

The benefits of reinforcing fibers on the mechanical properties of resins hardly need comment. However fiber reinforcement also has an effect on wear properties. The two materials most commonly used to reinforce lubricated thermoplastics are glass and carbon fibers.

Glass fibers

By improving creep resistance, thermal conductivity and heat distortion, glass reinforcement markedly improves the LPV of a base resin. Wear resistance may also be improved.

The degree of improvement is

Table 3. Wear and

Stationary surface	
Base Resin	Filler system
Polycarbonate	10% PTFE
Polycarbonate	15% PTFE 20% Glass fiber
Acetal copolymer	—
Acetal copolymer	—
Acetal copolymer	20% PTFE
Acetal copolymer	20% PTFE
PPS	10% Graphite 30% Glass fiber
PPS	15% PTFE 30% Glass fiber
PPS	15% PTFE 30% Glass fiber
Nylon 6/10	15% PTFE 30% Glass fiber
Nylon 6/10	15% PTFE 30% Glass fiber
Nylon 6/6	—
Nylon 6/6	—
Nylon 6/6	20% PTFE
Polyester (PBT)	—
Polyester (PBT)	20% PTFE

directly related to the efficiency of the sizing system that bonds the glass fiber to the resin. Glass beads and milled glass fibers (L/D less than 20), because they usually lack adequate sizing, can be expected to increase the wear factor (K) of a resin. In addition glass fibers and glass fillers also increase wear on the mating surface and increase the coefficients of friction.

Silicone and/or PTFE lubricants added to glass fiber-reinforced resins will, in many cases, inhibit the wear caused by the glass fibers. Silicone should not be used as the sole lubricant, however. PTFE provides far

Table 3. Wear properties of plastic on plastic

Moving surface		Wear factor, K of stationary surface 10^{-10} in ³ min/ ft/lb/hr	Coefficient of friction	
Base resin	Filler system		Static (40 psi)	Dynamic (40 psi, 50 fpm)
Nylon 6/10	15% PTFE 30% Glass fiber	35	0.40	0.05
Nylon 6/10	15% PTFE 30% Glass fiber	15	0.05	0.07
Against itself	—	10,200	0.19	0.15
Nylon 6/6	—	55	0.04	0.05
Against itself	—	35	0.10	0.09
Nylon 6/6	20% PTFE	30	0.03	0.04
Against itself	—	800	0.16	0.13
Against itself	—	160	0.08	0.07
PPS	10% Graphite 30% Glass fiber	750	0.13	0.12
Polycarbonate	10% PTFE	15	0.04	0.06
Polycarbonate	15% PTFE 20% Glass fiber	18	0.05	0.07
Against itself	—	1,150	0.12	0.21
Acetal copolymer	—	49	0.04	0.05
Against itself	—	30	0.08	0.05
Against itself	—	2,500	0.17	0.24
Against itself	—	40	0.10	0.08

more protection to the mating surface and should be specified (with or without silicone) if the wear rate of the mating surface must be minimized.

Carbon fibers

Carbon fibers impart to injection-molding thermoplastics the highest strength, modulus, HDT, creep and fatigue endurance values commercially available. These property improvements, along with greatly increased thermal conductivity and low coefficients of friction, make carbon fibers the ideal reinforcement for wear and friction applications.

With the addition of 30% carbon fibers, K factors as low as 20 can be achieved. Unlike glass fibers, carbon fibers reduce the coefficients of friction in the base polymer. The amount of reduction depends on the degree of graphitization of the carbon.

Since the LPV of a thermoplastic is directly related to its thermal conductivity and creep resistance, glass fiber can increase the operating limits of a plastic part. These limits can be increased still further by replacing the glass with carbon fibers. Also since the carbon is less abrasive than glass, carbon fibers will sharply reduce the

wear rate of the mating surface.

Another useful feature of carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastics is their low volume- and surface resistivities. Most resin systems containing 15% or more carbon fibers will effectively dissipate a static charge, a problem common to many thermoplastic gears and bearings used in business machines, textile equipment; etc. Internal lubricants can be used with carbon fibers to further improve the surface characteristics of most thermoplastics.

Plastic on plastic

With the rapid evolution of all-plastic assemblies in gear trains, pumps, blowers and similar products, predicting wear on a plastic-plastic interface has become a highly practical problem. The remainder of this article focuses on plastic-plastic wear.

Because plastics are not rigid bodies, they do not behave according to the classic laws of friction. As noted earlier, frictional forces are not proportional to load; friction increases with increasing speed. Also the static coefficient of friction is lower than the dynamic coefficient.

When viscoelastic, low-modulus materials are run against each other, additional inconsistencies crop up. For example, as shown in Table 3, the static coefficient of friction of acetal on acetal is 0.19; on steel it is only 0.14. On the other hand, the static coefficient of friction of nylon 6/6 versus itself is 0.12, while for nylon 6/6 on steel, the coefficient is 0.20.

Despite these anomalies, one trend is clear: when a thermoplastic is run against itself, the wear factor is extremely high unless the operating temperature and pressure are kept very low. Thus the wear factor (K) of acetal on acetal running at 40 psi and 50 fpm is 10,200; for acetal against steel, the K factor is 65.

In all-plastic assemblies the wear rate can be reduced, if crystalline resins are used, by selecting dissimilar plastics. Thus, if one of two acetal components is replaced by nylon 6/6, the K factor drops from 10,200 to 30, an acceptable value for most applications.

If amorphous resins are involved, or if environmental or manufacturing considerations require that only one plastic compound be used, the compound should contain an internal lubricant. Loadings of 15-20% PTFE have proven extremely effective. If 20% PTFE is added to an acetal vs. acetal system, the K factor is reduced from 10,200 to 35 under the same conditions.